

Data Storage game (Storage possibilities)

FAIR-vault

FRDN.

VSC

Vlaams Super Computer Centrum

FRDN.

LOCAL STORAGE

External Hard disk

Flash drive

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ON PREM(ISE)

Institutional

FRDN.

CLOUD

Personal Drive

Shared

FRDN.

SMART NOTEBOOKS

*ERN^{*1} ELN^{*2} EDC^{*3} Smartnotebook^{*4}*

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REPOSITORY

General

Discipline Specific

FRDN.

OTHER

FRDN.

Data storage game

Instructions

Bored of giving passive info sessions?

Are you bored just giving the info about possible data storage spaces?

Maybe this interactive game is an idea to bring some variation. We developed this interactive game to give a hands-on to choosing the correct data infrastructure.

Snake ladder game

You all know the snake ladder game, right? For sure the ones who have kids or played this in their childhood...

Resources

A2/A3 board snake ladder game

10 data storage solution cards

10 data storage general explanation cards

6 use cases

Practical

The data storage cards are as big as a name tag card, that way it can be used in a name tag holder. The explanation of the data storage places can be placed on the back.

Number of players: Minimum 2 players. For more than 5 players you could work with groups.

Examples:

use case

data storage solutions

How does it work?

Beginning: Each player can represent one or two data storage locations and pin the cards on themselves or put them in front of themselves. On the back of the data storage solutions there is general advice. They can't look at that yet with the exception of the Electronic Notebook card. The Electronic Notebook card contains the explanations of the abbreviations on the back.

Each round:

You roll the dice and go to the nearest “beginning of a ladder” or “ending of a snake”. If you are at the beginning of a ladder you can go up if your answer is correct otherwise you need to stay at the same position. For the end of the snake if your answer is incorrect you need to go back down otherwise you can stay at the same position.

Each number at the beginning of a ladder or ending of a snake matches with the number of a specific use case. For the use case, the correct data storage persona needs to be chosen both for during and after the research, keeping open science in mind. The data storage persona can look at the back to look at the general advice (on the back of the name tag) to see if it is a possible correct solution to the use case.

Winning:

When you reach number 30.

We have a new data storage expert!

Need to adapt the data storage game?

Hasselt University tried to make the data storage places as general as possible. Need to adapt the game according to your own institution? Feel free to send a mail to rdm@uhasselt.be

The RDM-team of Hasselt University wish you lots of fun using this data storage game!

Data Storage game (Explanation of the storage possibilities)

FAIR-vault

FAIR-vault/ Safe storage location
Is the **ADVISED** place to store sensitive data

This can also be stored on the shared drive
in case of:

- Correct access control
(Authorization, Authentication)
- Encryption

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VSC

VSC is an **ADVISED** medium for:
High performance computing

This consortium brings together knowhow in
scientific and technical computing

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LOCAL STORAGE

Local storage is a **NOT ADVISED** medium

Higher change of data loss:

- By theft, if device is not encrypted
- By defect data, no back-up=no data

No other alternatives?

External hard disk are tolerated
in dialogue with IT

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ON PREM

Shared = an **ADVISED** medium for:
Data storage during research.

Local storage = a **NOT ADVISED** medium

Researcher are obliged to share data with at
least the promotor. **Not shared?**
GDPR says we are not allowed
to get data from the personal drive

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CLOUD

Shared cloud= a **ADVISED** medium for: Data
storage during research.

Local storage = a **NOT ADVISED** medium

Researcher are obliged to share data with at
least the promotor.

Not shared? GDPR wise not allowed
to get data from personal drive

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RESEARCH NOTEBOOKS

1. ERN= Electronic research notebooks

For qualitative theoretical research

2. ELN= Electronic Lab Notebooks

For logging of experiments.

3. EDC= Electronic Data Capture

For clinical research

4. Smartnotebook

Scannable Whiteboard book

For lab's lacking computers, tablets

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REPOSITORY

Discipline-specific repository

ADVISED platform for data after research.

General repository

ADVISED if no discipline-specific platform

! At all times share a least the metadata

As open as possible
as closed as needed!

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OTHER

Do you know any other solutions?

Write them down on the "other solutions paper"

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